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Research Article

**A DESCRIPTIVE CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY TO ASSESS THE
ONSET OF DISCOMFORT AND PAIN DURING AND AFTER
ROOT PLANING AND SCALING**¹Dr. Owais Ahmad, ²Dr. Maria Afzal, ³Dr. Bilal Ahmad¹MO RHC Qadirabad DG Khan²Women Medical Officer, Government Maternity Hospital Pathi Ground Lahore³BHU Noor Jamal Tehsil Kharian, Gujrat**Abstract:**

Objective: In this particular research we aimed to determine the onset of various degrees of pain and discomfort during and after the periodontal debridement and periodontal probing as experienced by the patients. In order to find out this onset of pain and discomfort, we used VAS (Visual Analog Scale).

Methodology: Our cross-sectional descriptive research was carried out at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore in the timeframe of November 2016 to June 2017 (Periodontology Department). We carried out all the measurements in order to probe the depths and noted the incidence of pain and discomfort among all the patients through VAS. The hygienists also used VAS to complete his measurements and estimated level of pain and discomfort among patients as experienced by them and also taken the perception of the patients.

Results: Research sample consisted of 106 patients including both male and female with a respective number of 56 and 50. Research population had a slightly more male dominance. All the male and female patients received root planing and scaling procedures. About seventy percent of patients faced low response of the pain through instrumentation and probing with mild pain, moderate pain and severe pain having respective proportions of 36.6%, 33.3% and 13.3%. Research outcomes reflect that mild, moderate and severe pain was experienced by all the patients with varying proportions; furthermore, it was reported low during the procedure as during procedure pain was 23.3% and discomfort was 53% which increased after the procedure. The increase in pain was 23.3% to 53.3%; whereas, the increase in discomfort was from 53% to 86.7%.

Conclusion: A number of patients experienced various degrees of pain such as from mild pain to moderate and even severe pain in the course of root planing and scaling. Furthermore, the intensity of the discomfort and pain was more after the procedure in comparison to during the procedures.

Keywords: Scaling & Root Planing (SRP), Pain Intensity, VAS (Visual Analog Scale), Discomfort, Mild, Severe, Moderate and Probing.

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain refers to the unpleasant and unfriendly feeling which has an association with damaging and intense stimuli; whereas, discomfort refers to any uncomfortable state or feeling within the body or even caused by an outer object. Root planning and scaling aim at the removal of etiological agents which is a conservative periodontal treatment, deep cleaning or non-surgical periodontal treatment as these etiological agents may cause infection and inflammation such as calculus, dental plaque or its associated products [1]. Root planning and scaling help to prevent such instances and they are effective for disease prevention [2]. An onset of postoperative pain is not good for the surgical interventions of periodontal which needs proper reduction and prevention [3].

Periodontal diseases refer to a state in which an inflammatory condition develops causing damage to the periodontal tissues; it may also result in the shape of periodontitis or gingivitis. Such problems are better handled through various treatment options which include root planning or scaling depending on the severity of inflammation and disease [4].

The VAS method is very much effective and simple to assess the pain intensity and variation among various pain degrees as experienced by the patients [11 – 13]. Clinical practice often uses VAS to verify and validate different pain measurements in their routine practice, there are few other methods available but we opted for the VAS for its simplicity and effectiveness. In this particular research, we aimed to determine the onset of various degrees of pain and discomfort during and after the periodontal debridement and periodontal probing as experienced by the patients. In order to find out this onset of pain and discomfort, we used VAS (Visual Analog Scale).

METHODOLOGY:

Our cross-sectional descriptive research was carried out at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore in the timeframe of November 2016 to June 2017 (Periodontology Department). We carried out all the measurements in order to probe the depths and noted the incidence of pain and discomfort among all the

patients through VAS. The hygienists also used VAS to complete his measurements and estimated level of pain and discomfort among patients as experienced by them and also taken the perception of the patients.

Research sample selection was made through simple random sampling technique and we enrolled 106 patients from both genders. We shortlisted regular periodontal department patients in this series. There was no such consideration of age among patients who were undergoing root planning and scaling at the periodontal department of the hospital. We did not include any patient of a systemic disease, DM (Diabetes Mellitus), coagulopathies, hypertension, cardiac disease and hepatitis. A total of 106 patients completed the anxiety questionnaire and also submitted their consent to be a part of the research study. Treatment was carried out by demonstrators in fifty patients; whereas, consultants treated other 56 patients through ultrasonic scaling. Demonstrators also performed three measurements in the right lower quadrant of every patient and assessed the severity of the pain through VAS and also documented every outcome for further statistical analysis.

RESULTS:

The research sample consisted of 106 patients including both male and female with a respective number of 56 and 50. Research population had a slightly more male dominance. All the male and female patients received root planning and scaling procedures. About seventy percent patients faced low response of the pain through instrumentation and probing with mild pain, moderate pain and severe pain having respective proportions of 36.6%, 33.3% and 13.3% (Table – I). Research outcomes reflect that mild, moderate and severe pain was experienced by all the patients with varying proportions; furthermore, it was reported low during the procedure as during procedure pain was 23.3% and discomfort was 53% which increased after the procedure. The increase in pain was 23.3% to 53.3%; whereas, the increase in discomfort was from 53% to 86.7% (Table – II & III). Detailed outcomes of various pain severity degrees, during the procedure and after the procedure pain and discomfort outcomes are available in the given tabular data.

Table – I: Frequency of Various Pain Degrees among 106 Patients

The intensity of the Pain	Number of Patients	Percentage
No Pain	17	16.6
The mild onset of Pain	39	36.7
The moderate onset of Pain	36	33.4
Severe onset of Pain	14	13.3

Table – II: Frequency of Pain During and After the Procedure among 106 Patients

During Procedure Pain (106)	Present	Number	25
		Percentage	23.3
	Absent	Number	81
		Percentage	76.7
After Treatment Pain (106)	Present	Number	56
		Percentage	53.3
	Absent	Number	50
		Percentage	46.6

Table – III: Frequency of Discomfort During and After the Procedure among 106 Patients

During Procedure Discomfort (106)	Present	Number	56
		Percentage	53
	Absent	Number	50
		Percentage	47
After Treatment Discomfort (106)	Present	Number	92
		Percentage	86.7
	Absent	Number	14
		Percentage	13.3

DISCUSSION:

We reported the outcomes of pain and discomfort during and after the procedures among patients especially for root planing and scaling during the procedure and postoperatively through VAS; Canakci also reported various outcomes of pain, postoperative pain, discomfort and dentin sensitivity through VAS [2]. There was no significant variation in the outcomes of pain and discomfort as both the authors used VAS to present possible increase in the level of discomfort and pain during and after periodontal management [5, 6].

Braun A used an ultrasonic scaler in order to treat periodontal patients. He extended conventional periodontal management to the patients and used VAS for the assessment of pain and discomfort among patients for the measurement of pain and discomfort after every treatment cycle. The outcomes about the pain intensity are same as reported in this particular series. Braun is of the view that with the help of Er: YAG type Laser in the course of supportive periodontal management; we can reduce the painful sensations experienced by the patients than sonic scaler tools and instrumentation [6].

Variation in pain intensity can be measured through VAS accurately and effectively as it is a widely used assessment method [7, 8]. Bruce L also carried out similar research and assessed pain duration and intensity after scaling and root planing but instead of VAS, he employed a self-assessment pain scale named as "Heft-Parker" [9]. There may be possible variation in the discomfort and pain with respect to gender, age, mouth region, the surface of the tooth, tooth type, probing depth, bleeding and other associated parameters [10, 11]. This research had no age limitations for the research sample selection.

CONCLUSION:

In the light of abovesaid, we can conclude that pain and discomfort during the procedure were less than the pain and discomfort felt after the procedures of root planing and scaling. This variation can be attributed to the anaesthetic agents which were used in the course of scaling and root planing. Consultants should advise powerful analgesics, appropriate antibiotics and anti-hypersensitive toothpaste to patients for the reduction of postoperative discomfort and pain. A number of patients experienced various degrees of pain such as from mild pain to moderate and even severe pain in the course of root planing and scaling. Furthermore, the intensity of the discomfort and pain was more after the procedure in comparison to during the procedures.

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